

6.3 Neutron time-of-flight (TOF) powder diffraction

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Neutron time-of-flight (TOF) powder diffraction [1] is a powerful technique for solving crystal structures and investigating structural properties on the atomic/molecular level. It is applied on modern materials across various scientific fields, utilizing the neutrons unique capabilities in numerous aspects.

TOF powder diffraction typically utilizes a pulsed neutron beam with a wide angular coverage detector system to simultaneously probe the lattice space distances d via tof/λ and 2θ according to Bragg's law. Hence, when neutrons interact with a powdered sample, they are detected at different scattering angles depending on the material's crystal structure. By measuring the time from the pulse generation till reaching the detector for each neutron scattered at the sample, one can also reassign the wavelength.

In general, powder diffraction is used within many different scientific communities and also materials, such like cements, lithium-ion batteries, fuel cell materials, hydrogen storage materials, magnetic materials, all kinds of oxides, or more advanced, possibly air- or moisture sensitive chemical compounds, etc.. The particular strength of (TOF) neutron powder diffraction manifests, when unique information that is not available by complementary methods become accessible to characterize the materials structure or the structural behavior with changing temperature, pressure, electric or magnetic field, etc. and eventual phase-transitions occur. Finally, in situ or operando studies, e.g., of ongoing chemical reactions need to be mentioned. [2]

Typical examples are samples with light elements like for example hydrogen or lithium next to heavy atoms, e.g., in batteries or more generally in energy or hydrogen storage materials. Similarly, also neighboring elements or even isotopes, e.g., hydrogen and deuterium can be nicely distinguished within neutron diffraction.

Another domain of neutron scattering in general and also neutron TOF powder diffraction is the analysis of magnetic systems, because of the neutron's magnetic dipole moment. Examples are samples that show cooperative magnetism, such as ferro-, antiferro- or ferrimagnetism, or even more complicated quantum phenomes.

In the following we present a set of metadata tailored to neutron TOF powder diffraction experiments. As an example, we apply the proposed schema to a hypothetical experiment at the POWTEX [3] instrument located at the FRM-II. Herein, we want to give special emphasis to the entry 'Instrument: configuration used, installed options' since this should include all needed parameters for data reduction, e.g., within PowderReduceP2D function of Mantid [4], a reference to the current instrument definition file (at the time of the experiment) and also the set of fundamental instrument description (FID) parameters [5].

[1] Dronskowski, R. et al. "Neutron diffraction: a primer" *Zeitschrift für Kristallographie - Crystalline Materials*, vol. 239, no. 5-6, 2024, pp. 139-166. <https://doi.org/10.1515/zkri-2024-0001>

[2] Kisi, E. H. and Howard, C. J. “Applications of Neutron Powder Diffraction” *Oxford University Press*, 2008. ISBN: 9780199657421.

[3] Houben, A. et al. “New neutron-guide concepts and simulation results for the POWTEX instrument” *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section A*, vol. 680, 2012, pp. 124-133. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nima.2012.03.015>.

[4] Arnold, O. et al. “Mantid-Data Analysis and Visualization Package for Neutron Scattering and mu-SR Experiments”. *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section A*, vol. 764, 2014, pp. 156-166. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nima.2014.07.029>.

[5] Houben, A. et al. “POWTEX visits POWGEN” *Journal of Applied Crystallography*, vol 56, part 3, 2023, pp. 633-642. <https://doi.org/10.1107/S1600576723002819>.

Dataset

Metadata Field	Type	Comment	Usecase example or possible values for POWTEX
Identifier	Uuid		
Identifier / name	Data set name	Human readable name	
Start time	Date/time	Of the measurement/run, applies to file	
End time	Date/time	Of the measurement/run, applies to file	
Sample ID	PID of sample	PID (external or local ID)	
Data format		Ideally nexus format is used	
Title / description	Free text	Short description of the measurement/run	Calibration measurement with vanadium

<p>Instrument: configuration used, installed options</p>	<p>All needed, example</p> <p>Keywords see</p>	<p>description of installed options and links to any further information on the used instrument setup, e.g. detector type, detector position, neutron guide type, wavelength band</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Instrument description: POWTEX IDF 2025 - Wavelength band: 1 - Pulse-Frequency frequency: 200 Hz (100, 200, 400, 480, 500, 600, 666, 800, 1000, 2000, 2200) Hz - ratio P10 chopper: 1 (1, 11/15, 33/40, 22/25, 55/60) - ratio P11 chopper: 1 (1, 10/11, 5/11, 20/33, 15/22, 21/22) - ratio OC chopper: 1/2 (0, 1/2) - ratio BC chopper: 1/2 (0, 1/2) - neutron guide changer positions: 1,1,1 (1,1,1; 1,1,0; 1,0,0; 2,2,2; 2,2,2,3) [in principle any combination of 1 = default guide; 0 = absorbing; 2 = higher reflectivity) - roof detectors: used (used/not used) - FID parameters: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Type:PN2 o fltPath:60.0 o 2-theta:90.0 o difC:22591.86 o difA:0.0 o difB:0.0 o Zero:0.0 o alpha-0:500.0 o alpha-1:1.05387 o beta-0:500.0 o beta-1:0.0 o beta-q:0.0 o sig-0:0.0 o sig-1:0.0
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Metadata Field	Type	Comment	Usecase example or possible values for POWTEX
			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ sig-2:0.0 ○ sig-q:0.0 ○ X:0.0 ○ Y:0.0 ○ Z:0.0 ○ Azimuth:0.0 ○ pfType:8 ○ L2A:0.81 ○ L2B:0.0 ○ div:0.001919862 ○ W-Pixel:0.0 ○ Dtt:0.000623 ○ DL:0.002 ○ DthF:0.969 ○ Add:0.00148 ○ W-Sample:0.00433 ○ Eta:0.21 ○ DthDet:0.00678 ○ Bank:1
Measurement technique(s)	Free text	PaNET ontology ²⁰ if possible or free text	Neutron Time-of-Flight Powder Diffraction
Environment conditions / settings	Key value pairs; name, value, unit	as many key value pairs (or time-log series) as needed, also for automatic data processing and analysis, e.g. temperature, pressure, magnetic field	Temperature, 300, K
Measurement mode	Keyword	Identifying the free variable during the run/measurement, e.g. temperature, pressure, magnetic field, time	Time
Sample environment: installed options	Choice of different sample environment options by keyword, free text or sample environment PID		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cryofurnace, JANIS cryostat, mirror oven, uniaxial press, free sample stage - Globular collimator: used (used, not used)

Metadata Field	Type	Comment	Usecase example or possible values for POWTEX
Purpose of data set	Choose between: measurement / calibration / sample / background / alignment / ...		calibration
References	Link, Identifier	e.g. calibration data	ID of vanadium and empty measurement
Comments	Free Text	Add comments after the measurement, e.g. to note mistakes, failures etc. Can also be provided automatically via instrument control software	Beam down after 1 h
Quality metrics	Free text	Data quality metrics is a number given by the user to rate the dataset	10/10
Analysis status	Choose between: analysis planned / analysis ongoing / analysis finished / intend to publish / published / analysis not possible / open to outside analysis	Allow user to give an indication on the analysis status. If dataset cannot or will not be analyzed this can also be highlighted here.	Open to outside analysis

Sample

Metadata Field	Type	Comment 1	Usecase example POWTEX
Name	Free text	Human readable name	Vanadium
Local ID			
Ext PID	Link		
Registration schema		If externally registered	
Agency		If externally registered	
Key words		following e.g. PhySH	
Description	Free text	Description of sample	Vanadium powder

Metadata Field	Type	Comment 1	Usecase example POWTEX
Chemical composition		e.g. CAS number, SMILE, InCh	V
Common name	Free text	If applicable	Vanadium
State	Choose between: liquid / powder / single crystal / solid / thin film / in situ		Powder
Mass	Value, unit pair	If applicable	200 mg
Crystal structure	Structural archetype and/or space group number according to IUCR	If applicable	Vanadium, I m-3 m
Unit cell parameters	Multiple value, unit pairs	If applicable	a = 3.02710 Å
Preparation date	Date	If applicable	
Supplier / creator			
Relationships	Parent sample ID	If applicable	
Additional fields		Any additional information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sample container shape: sphere (sphere) - Sample container diameter: 10 (5, 8, 10, 12), mm - Sample container material: Vanadium (Vanadium, Glas)